

Supplemental File 1

1. Descriptive Information

2. Supplemental Table 1: Codebook for RQ1 and RQ2 analysis

3. Supplemental Table 2: Codebook for RQ3 analysis

4. References

1. Descriptive Information

Variable Name	Description
caseid	Label each individual slogan as an individual case.
slogan	The title of the campaign slogan, including words, grammar and punctuation.
brand_organization	The brand or organization responsible for the slogan.
campaign_category	The advertisement's affiliated U.S. media campaign typology, as assigned by Kraak et al. (2022)
1 = corporate advertising, marketing or entertainment campaigns	
2 = corporate social responsibility, public relations, or cause marketing campaigns	
3 = social marketing campaigns	
4 = public information, awareness, education or health promotion campaigns	
5 = media advocacy or countermarketing campaigns	
6 = political or public policy campaigns	
year	The date the campaign was launched.

2. Supplemental Table 1: Codebook for RQ1 and RQ2 analysis

APPEALS

Variable Name	Description
rational	<i>The rational variable name denotes a rational appeal.</i>
0 = No	

1 = Yes

The campaign tagline or slogan aims to persuade audiences through rational thought processes and logical information to appeal to one's reason. The tagline or slogan provides the audience with fact-based and verifiable information about the product or brand, persuades by means of logical information and presentation of facts and data, or by raising awareness by means of presenting information (Casias & Pereira, 2021).

Only information within the text of the campaign slogan may be used to make this determination; images, background information about the campaign will not be used.

***Casais and Pereira (2021) use the term categories of analysis for the appeals that are listed alphabetically and defined below.**

Rational appeals include: comparative, factual, scarcity and solutions (n=4).

Emotional appeals include: positive emotional appeals (i.e., humor, pleasure, pride, relaxed, sexual and social) (n=6); negative emotional appeals (i.e., anger, disgust, fear, guilt and worry) (n=5); and co-active emotional appeals (n=1).

comparative

0 = No

1 = Yes

"Either directly or indirectly naming competitors in an advertisement and comparing one or more specific attributes" (Wilkie & Farris, 1975, p. 7; Hornick et al., 2016, p. 198).

factual

0 = No

1 = Yes

Something that is presented as having happened or existing, especially something for which proof exists, or about which there is information (Cambridge Dictionary). To think about something in a logical, sensible way (Oxford English Dictionary) grounded in evidence or factual information. Thinking in which logical processes of an inductive or deductive character are used to draw conclusions from facts or premises or both. (APA Dictionary of Psychology).

The tagline or slogan may include product-related information, including specific references to calories, price, process, or ingredients (Finn & Strickland, 1982, p. 984).

scarcity

0 = No

1 = Yes

The tagline or slogan seeks to "induce product purchase by triggering consumer inferences about product quality and/or product desirability," as well as consumers' desire for uniqueness or psychological reactance motivation (Aguirre-Rodriguez, 2013, p. 371).

solutions

0 = No

1 = Yes

A proposed actionable strategy or means to help an individual solve a problem or deal with a situation at individual, local, or global levels. Presented solutions are concrete and not just abstract or motivational.

EMOTIONAL APPEALS

emotional

0 = No

1 = Yes

The emotional variable name denotes an emotional appeal strategy.

The campaign tagline or slogan aims to persuade the target audience to prefer, buy or consume a product or a specific brand; or discontinue a behavior using affective stimuli that influences their emotions. The tagline or slogan may use positive appeals (i.e., arousal, enthusiasm or pleasure); negative appeals (i.e., anger, disgust or fear); or both (Casais & Pereira, 2021).

Only information within the text of the campaign slogan may be used to make this determination; images, background information about the campaign will not be used.

Viewers can perceive emotional appeals as either positive (pleasant), negative (unpleasant), or co-active (a combination of both positive and negative). Emotional appeals will be divided into three domains (positive, negative, coactive) based on valence or tone and operationalized below.

POSITIVE APPEAL

positive

0 = No

1 = Yes

The positive variable name denotes a positive emotional appeal.

The campaign tagline or slogan offers an incentive or benefits related to one's behavior to buy or consume a product, adopt a specific brand, or discontinue a behavior.

The tagline or slogan may include strategies such as humor, happiness, hope, pride, or love. Examples of words potentially used in this category include terms pertaining to life, health, smile, love, respect, protect, good, responsibility, save, gains, efficacy. The slogan may include rhetoric involving humor, empathy, motivating, and advising (Casais & Proenca, 2021).

Only information within the text of the campaign slogan may be used to make this determination; images, background information about the campaign will not be used.

Casais and Pereira (2021) list these as types of positive appeals or categories of analysis.

Types of emotional appeals (categories of analysis) are presented alphabetically and defined below.

Emotional appeals include: positive emotional appeals (i.e., humor, pleasure, pride, relaxed, sexual and social) (n=6); negative emotional appeals (i.e., anger, disgust, fear, guilt and worry) (n=5); and co-active emotional appeal (n=1).

humor
0 = No
1 = Yes

The capacity to perceive or express the amusing aspects of a situation (APA Dictionary of Psychology).

relaxed
0 = No
1 = Yes

The tagline or slogan implies “warmth, a highly positive emotion that people enjoy in their relationships with family or friends” (Mensa et al., 2020, p. 4) and may include a “suggestion that this product will help you unwind” (Finn & Strickland, 1982, p. 987) or provide comfort (Cheng & Schweitzer, 1996).

This category includes relief.

sexual
0 = No
1 = Yes

References to a “sexual encounter” or inclusion of “references in the text of the ad such as naughty, discreet, tempting” (Finn & Strickland, 1982, p. 986). It may also reference “a romantic setting” or words like “passion” that are “connected to sex appeal or romance” (Friedman et al., 2018, p. 6).

This category includes romantic.

social
0 = No
1 = Yes

The tagline or slogan may reflect individuals enjoying active lifestyles, parties (Friedman et al., 2018, p. 6) or other occasions that suggest shared, social experiences (Finn & Strickland, 1982, p. 986).

“The use of a product is claimed to be able to elevate the position or rank of the user in the eyes of others.” Product use conveys feelings of prestige and trendsetting (Cheng & Schweitzer, 1996, p. 30).

It may indicate wealth or affluence through “general references to success in terms of high social or economic status.” It may also attempt to associate the product with some form of social success (Finn & Strickland, 1982, p. 988).

This category includes affluence, acceptance, belonging, success and status.

NEGATIVE APPEAL

negative
0 = No
1 = Yes

The negative variable name denotes a negative emotional appeal.
The campaign tagline or slogan aims to evoke discomfort or emotional imbalance toward a product or brand. The tagline or slogan may elicit anger, disgust, fear, guilt, shame, worry or threat in the target audience to disincentivize buying or using a product or brand (Casais & Pereira, 2021; Casais & Proença, 2021).

This category includes consequences, danger, death, disability, disease, fatality, fear, guilt, loss, shame or threat.

Only information within the text of the campaign slogan may be used to make this determination; images, background information about the campaign will not be used.

Types of negative emotional appeals (n=5), also called categories of analysis,* are listed alphabetically and defined below.

***Casais and Pereira (2021) list these as types of negative appeals or categories of analysis.**

Anger
0 = No
1 = Yes

Definition: A strong feeling of displeasure, dissatisfaction, or annoyance, generally combined with antagonism or hostility towards a particular cause or object (Oxford English Dictionary). An emotion characterized by tension and hostility arising from frustration, real or imagined injury by another, or perceived injustice. It can manifest itself in behaviors designed to remove the object of the anger or behaviors designed merely to express the emotion (APA Dictionary of Psychology).

Disgust
0 = No
1 = Yes

Definition: "A feeling of revulsion or strong disapproval aroused by something unpleasant or offensive" (Wang et al., 2021, p. 5).

This category includes revolt, repulse, nausea, unappetizing and unpalatable.

Fear
0 = No
1 = Yes

Definition: A basic, intense emotion aroused by the detection of imminent threat or consequences of one's choices or actions, involving an immediate alarm reaction or longer-term effect on behaviors that mobilizes the organism by triggering a set of physiological changes (APA Dictionary of Psychology).

Guilt
0 = No
1 = Yes

Definition: A failure of duty, delinquency; offense, crime, sin (Oxford English Dictionary). May also refer to a self-conscious emotion characterized by a painful appraisal of having done (or thought) something that is wrong and often by a readiness to take action designed to undo or mitigate this wrong (APA Dictionary of Psychology). This code may include guilt based on a previous action or may reflect guilt on an anticipatory basis. an emotional state that involves feelings of remorse, self-blame and self-punishment experienced after committing an action or contemplating future violation of internalized or socially acceptable standards of behavior.

An emotional state that involves feelings of remorse, self-blame and self-punishment experienced after committing an action or contemplating future violation of internalized or socially acceptable standards of behavior. There are three types of guilt: reactive, anticipatory and existential guilt. There are three types of guilt: reactive, anticipatory and existential guilt (Huhmann & Brotherton, 1997).

This category includes remorse, regret, and sorrow.

Worry

0 = No

1 = Yes

Definition: A state of mental distress or agitation due to concern about an impending or anticipated event, threat, or danger (APA Dictionary of Psychology).

COACTIVE APPEAL

coactive

0 = No

1 = Yes

The coactive variable name denotes a coactive/mixed emotional appeal.

The campaign slogan contains both positive and negative emotional appeals or a mixed state of emotions. Thus, they induced both positive and negative feelings at the same time (see Yousef, Dietrich, & Rundle-Thiele, 2021). Only information within the text of the campaign slogan may be used to make this determination; images, background information about the campaign will not be used.

3. Supplemental Table 2: Codebook for RQ3 analysis

VARIABLE NAME

DESCRIPTION

caseid

Label each individual advertisement as an individual case.

Image

The advertisement image.

Brand_organization

The brand or organization responsible for the slogan.

Campaign_category

1 = corporate advertising, marketing or entertainment campaigns

2 = corporate social responsibility, public relations, or cause marketing campaigns

3 = social marketing campaigns

4 = public information, awareness, education or health promotion campaigns

5 = media advocacy or countermarketing campaigns

6 = political or public policy campaigns

The advertisement's affiliated U.S. media campaign typology, as assigned by Kraak et al. (2022).

People (5 variables)

- 0 = No
- 1 = Yes

The ‘people’ variable name denotes the inclusion of people in the advertisement. People may include celebrities and other public figures, historical figures, or models. This variable includes images that feature an entire body/face or those which feature only a small portion of the body, such as hands or a partial face. The advertisement’s visual elements may be used to make this determination; taglines, slogans, background information about the campaign will not be used.

Descriptions of people (categories of analysis) are listed below:

Note: Turner et al. (2020) list these as types of demographic elements or categories of analysis.

Biological_sex

- 0 = No individuals pictured
- 1 = Unclear
- 2 = Both male and female
- 3 = Male
- 4 = Female

The ‘biological or sex’ variable name denotes perceived biological sex of the person(s) pictured in the advertisement.

age

- 0 = No individuals pictured
- 1 = Unclear
- 2 = Multiple ages pictured
- 3 = Elementary school-aged children
- 4 = Teens/adolescents (up to age 18)
- 5 = Adults (18 and older)

The ‘age’ variable name denotes the perceived age of the person(s) pictured in the advertisement.

race_ethnicity

- 0 = No individuals pictured
- 1 = Unclear
- 2 = Multiple races or ethnicities
 pictured
- 3 = White
- 4 = Black
- 5 = Latinx or Hispanic
- 6 = Native American or Pacific
 Islander
- 7 = Asian

The ‘race or ethnicity’ variable name denotes a “crude estimate” of the perceived race and ethnicity of people pictured in the advertisement.

Perceived advertisement narratives and visual elements (categories of analysis) are listed below Casais & Proença (2015, 2021), Alkazemi & Van Stee (2020), and Clarke and Honeycutt (2000) define these as perceived advertisement narratives, visual elements, or categories of analysis.

emotion

- 0 = unclear
- 1 = positive
- 2 = negative

The ‘emotion’ variable name reflects the perceived emotional state of the person(s) in the advertisement. (Casais & Proença, 2021).

3 = coercive

'not applicable' emotion indicates the advertisement does not contain people or the perceived emotional state of the person(s) is not distinguishable.

A 'positive' emotion state shows "motivating/confident people, social models, testimonial, public figures" (Casais & Proença, 2021). Facial expressions and body language reflect those that "are typically associated with positive emotions," including "smiling, laughing, hugging, etc." (Alkazemi & Van Stee, 2020). A 'negative' emotion shows "frightened/worried people" (Casais & Proença, 2021). Facial expressions and body language reflect those that "are typically associated with negative emotions," such as "frowning, crying, etc." (Alkazemi & Van Stee, 2020).

content

- 0 = unclear
- 1 = positive
- 2 = negative
- 3 = coercive

The 'content' variable name reflects the "story content of the advertisements," including text and graphics (Casais & Proença, 2021).

'Unclear' story content indicates the advertisement does not contain story content or the valence (tone) of the story content is unclear or not distinguishable.

'Positive' story content shows the "benefits" of behaviors

'Negative' story content shows "negative or unwanted consequences" of behaviors

'Coactive' story content shows both the benefits and negative/unwanted consequences of a behavior

color

- 0 = multiple or no dominant color
- 1 = blue
- 2 = brown
- 3 = gray
- 4 = green
- 5 = orange
- 6 = red
- 7 = violet
- 8 = yellow
- 9 = black
- 10 = traffic light color scheme (red, amber yellow, green)
- 11 = patriotic color scheme (red, white, and blue)

The 'color' variable reflects the dominant color of the advertisement, meaning "the color that occupied the largest area of the ad," excluding black or white (Clarke & Honeycutt, 2000).

'No dominant color' indicates the advertisement did not feature a single dominant color.

The listed color options (blue, brown, gray, green, orange, red, violet, yellow) have "been established as standard hues that are readily observable in content analysis" (Clarke & Honeycutt, 2000).

Color_qualitative

Qualitatively note observances about the colors used in the advertisement. May include notes about emotions evoked by color scheme.

product

0 = absent

1 = present

The 'product image' variable name reflects the visual depiction of a product. This category excludes company logos (Alkazemi & Van Stee, 2020). This includes content, color, image and brand.

'Present' indicates the advertisement contains a visual depiction of the product

'Absent' indicates the advertisement does not contain a visual depiction of the product.

4. References

- Aguirre-Rodriguez, A. (2013). The effect of consumer persuasion knowledge on scarcity appeal persuasiveness. *Journal of Advertising*, 42(4), 371–379. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2013.803186>
- Alkazemi, M. F., & Van Stee, S. K. (2020). Electronic direct-to-consumer advertising of pharmaceuticals: An assessment of textual and visual content of websites. *Health Education Research*, 35(2), 134–151. <https://doi.org/10.1093/her/cyaa004>
- American Psychological Association. (2022). APA Dictionary of Psychology. <https://dictionary.apa.org/>
- Casais, B., & Pereira, A.C. (2021). The prevalence of emotional and rational tone in social advertising appeals. *RAUSP Manag J*, 56, 282–294. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RAUSP-08-2020-0187>
- Casais, B., & Proença, J.F. (2021). The use of positive and negative appeals in social advertising: a content analysis of television ads for preventing HIV/AIDS. *Int Rev Public Nonprofit Mark*, 19, 623–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12208-021-00318-y>
- Cheng, H. & Schweitzer, J. C. (1996). Cultural values reflected in Chinese and U.S. television commercials. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 36(3), 27–45. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1996-05352-002>
- Clarke I., & Honeycutt, E. D. (2000). Color usage in international business-to-business print advertising. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 29, 255–261. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501\(99\)00068-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501(99)00068-1)
- Finn, T. A. & Strickland, D. E. (1982). A content analysis of beverage alcohol advertising. *Journal of Studies on Alcohol*, 43(9), 964–989. <https://doi.org/10.15288/jsa.1982.43.964>
- Friedman, K. L., Roberts, M. E., Keller-Hamilton, B., Yates, K. A., Paskett, E. D., Berman, M. L., Slater, M. D., Lu, B., & Ferketich, A. K. (2018). Attitudes toward tobacco, alcohol, and non-alcohol beverage advertisement themes among adolescent boys. *Substance Use Misuse*, 53(10), 1706–1714. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826084.2018.1429473>
- Hornick, J., Ofir, C., & Rachamim, M. (2016). Qualitative evaluation of persuasive appeals using comparative meta-analysis. *The Communication Review*, 19(3), 192–222. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10714421.2016.1195204>
- Huhmann, B.A., & Brotherton, T.P. (1997). A content analysis of guilt appeals in popular magazine advertisements. *J Advertising*. 26(2), 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.1997.10673521>
- Kraak, V.I., Consavage Stanley, K., Harrigan, P.B., & Zhou, M. (2022). How have media campaigns been used to promote and discourage healthy and unhealthy beverages in the United States? A systematic scoping review to inform future research to reduce sugary beverage health risks to Americans. *Obesity Rev*, 23, e13425. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13425>
- Lustig, R.H. (2017). *The Hacking of the American Mind: The science behind the corporate takeover of our bodies and brains*. New York: Avery Random House LLC. <https://robertlustig.com/hacking/>
- Mensa, M., & Vargas-Bianchi, L. (2020). Nurtured and sorrowful: positive and negative emotional appeals in COVID-19 themed brand communications. *SocArXiv Papers*. <https://osf.io/preprints/socarxiv/68ukd/>
- Turner, M. M., Ford, L., Somerville, V., Javellana, D., Day, K. R., & Lapinski, M. K. (2020). The use of stigmatizing messaging in anti-obesity communications campaigns: Quantification of obesity and stigmatization. *Communication Reports*, 33(3), 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08934215.2020.1793375>
- Wang, X., Nan, X., & Stanley, S. J. (2021). Emotion and virality of food safety risk communication messages on social media. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 105(3), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.4148/1051-0834.2391>
- Wilkie, W., & Farris, P. (1975). Comparison advertising: Problems and potential. *Journal of Marketing*, 39(4), 7–15. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1250590>

Yousef, M., Dietrich, T., & Rundle-Thiele, S. (2021). Social advertising effectiveness in driving action: A study of positive, negative and coercive appeals on social media. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115954>

Supplemental File 2

Comprehensive list of 280 U.S. media campaigns, organized chronologically in the six media campaign typology categories, used for the RQ1 and RQ2 analysis, and 60 unique media campaigns used for the RQ3 analysis*

* The list includes 60 unique campaigns (86 media campaigns with 103 images) bolded in blue font below used for the RQ3 analysis.

Campaign Typology Category Campaign Name (national, city, state)	Date Launched
1. Corporate advertising, marketing or entertainment campaigns (n = 184)	
<i>The Coca-Cola Company</i> (national) (n = 81)	
Drink Coca-Cola and Enjoy It	1886
Delicious and Refreshing	1904
Coca-Cola Revives and Sustains	1905
The Great National Temperance Beverage	1906
Three Million a Day	1917
Thirst Knows No Season	1922
Enjoy Thirst	1923
Refresh Yourself	1924
Six Million A Day	1925
It Had to Be Good to Get Where It Is	1926
Pure as Sunlight	1927
Around the Corner from Everywhere	1927
The Pause that Refreshes	1929
Ice Cold Sunshine	1932
The Best Friend Thirst Ever Had	1938
Thirst Asks Nothing More	1939
Whoever You Are, Whatever You Do, Wherever You May Be, When You Think Refreshment Think of Ice Cold Coca-Cola	1939
The Only Thing Like Coca-Cola is Coca-Cola Itself	1942

Where There's Coke, There's Hospitality	1948
Along the Highway to Anywhere	1949
What You Want is a Coke	1952
Coca-Cola... Makes Good Things Taste Better	1956
Sign of Good Taste	1957
The Cold, Crisp Taste of Coke	1958
Be Really Refreshed	1959
Things Go Better with Coke	1963
It's the Real Thing	1969
Look Up America	1975
Coke Adds Life	1976
Have a Coke and a Smile	1976
Coke Is It!	1982
We've Got the Taste for You	1985
America's Real Choice	1985
Red, White & You	1986
Catch the Wave	1986
When Coca-Cola is a Part of Your Life, You Can't Beat the Feeling	1987
You Can't Beat the Feeling	1988
Official Soft Drink of Summer	1989
You Can't Beat the Real Thing	1990
Always Coca-Cola	1993
Taste It All (Diet Coke)	1993
This is Refreshment (Diet Coke)	1994
Obey Your Thirst (Sprite)	1994
The World Together. Always. (Olympic campaign)	1994
Just for the Taste of It	1996
Coca-Cola Incredible Summer	1997
Get Caught Red Handed	1997
Feed the Rush (Surge)	1997

Fully Loaded Summer (Surge)	1997
You are What You Drink (Diet Coke)	1998
Coke Card	1998
Surge Around the World (Surge)	1998
No Thirst is Safe (Citra grapefruit soda)	1998
Live Your Life (Diet Coke)	1999
Coca-Cola. Enjoy.	2000
It Could Be Your Next Coke	2000
Drink Sprite. Buy Rocketcash. Get What You Want.	2000
Life Tastes Good	2001
Nature's A Mother. Drink to It (Mad River Teas, Coca-Cola & Nestle joint venture)	2002
Coca-Cola.... Real	2003
Real, Make it Real	2005
The Coke Side of Life / Welcome to the Coke Side of Life	2006
Sip Stealing. Not a Felony in All 50 States.	2006
Real Coca-Cola Taste with Zero Calories (Coke Zero)	2007
Great Taste Has its Benefits (Coke Zero Plus)	2007
Don't Dew It (Vault)	2009
Don't Settle for An Incomplete Sports Drink (Powerade)	2009
Open Happiness	2009
Polar Bears Catch	2012
Liquid and Linked	2012
Move to the Beat (London Olympics teen campaign)	2012
Movement is Happiness	2013
Mirage (2013 Super Bowl campaign)	2013
The Ahh Effect	2013
Share a Coke	2014
It's Beautiful (2014 Super Bowl campaign)	2014
Get a Taste (Diet Coke)	2014

Taste the Feeling	2016
#ThatsGold Rio campaign	2016
The Letter	2020
Real Magic	2021
<i>PepsiCo Inc. (national) (n = 84)</i>	
Exhilarating, Invigorating, Aids Digestion	1903
Original Pure Food Drink	1907
Delicious and Healthful	1908
Drink Pepsi-Cola. It Will Satisfy You.	1913
For All Thirsts – Pepsi-Cola	1915
Pepsi-Cola – It Makes You Scintillate	1919
Peps You Up!	1928
Here’s Health!	1929
Sparkling, Delicious	1932
It’s the Best Cola Drink	1933
Double Size	1934
Refreshing and Healthful	1934
Bigger Drink, Better Taste	1934
Join the Swing to Pepsi-Cola	1938
Twice as Much for a Nickel	1939
It’s A Great American Custom	1947
Why Take Less When Pepsi’s Best	1949
More Bounce to the Ounce	1950
Any Weather is Pepsi Weather	1950
The Light Refreshment	1954
Refreshing Without Filling	1955
Say Pepsi, Please	1957
Be Sociable / Be Sociable, Have a Pepsi / The Sociables	1958
Now it’s Pepsi for Those Who Think Young	1961
Come Alive! You’re in the Pepsi Generation.	1963

Source: Kraak, V.I.; Consavage Stanley K.; Harrigan, P.B.; Zhou, M. How have media campaigns been used to promote and discourage healthy and unhealthy beverages in the United States? A systematic scoping review to inform future research to reduce sugary beverage health risks to Americans. *Obes. Rev.* **2022**, *23*, e13425. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13425>.

Taste that Beats the Others Cold. Pepsi Pours It On	1967
You've Got a Lot to Live. Pepsi's Got a Lot to Give.	1969
Join the Pepsi People, Feelin' Free	1973
Lipsmackin Thirst Quenchin Pepsi	1974
Have a Pepsi Day	1976
Catch that Pepsi Spirit	1979
Pepsi's Got Your Taste for Life	1981
Pepsi Now! Take the Challenge	1983
Pepsi. The Choice of a New Generation	1984
Pepsi. A Generation Ahead	1989
Gotta Have It / Chill Out	1991
The Choice is Yours	1992
Be Young, Have Fun, Drink Pepsi	1993
Right Now	1993
Double Dutch Bus	1994
Do the Dew (Mountain Dew)	1995
Nothing Else is a Pepsi	1995
Drink Pepsi. Get Stuff.	1995
Change the Script	1996
Generation Next	1997
This is Diet? (Diet Pepsi)	1997
It's the Cola	1998
For Those Who Think Young / The Joy of Pepsi-Cola	1999
I Love My Mug (Mug root beer)	1999
Ask for More	1999
Too Good to Be One Calorie. But It Is. (Pepsi One)	2000
Choose Your Music	2000
Share the Joy with Music	2000
The Joy of Pepsi	2001
Mountain Dew Pirate Radio	2001

Think Young Drink Young	2002
Pepsi – It’s the Cola	2003
Dare for More	2003
Why You Doggin’ Me / Taste the One That’s Forever Young	2006
Catch that Pepsi Spirit	2006
More Happy	2007
More Cola Taste (Diet Pepsi)	2007
Wake Up People! (Diet Pepsi Max)	2007
Pepsi is #1	2008
Something for Everyone	2008
Every Sip Brings You Closer (campaign for PepsiStuff.com)	2008
Yes You Can	2009
Zero Calories, Maximum Taste (Pepsi Max)	2009
Refresh Everything / Every Generation Refreshes the World	2009
Every Pepsi Refreshes the World	2010
Summer Time is Pepsi Time	2011
Born in the Carolinas	2011
Where There’s Pepsi, There’s Music	2012
Live for Now	2012
Change the Game	2012
The Best Drink Created Worldwide	2012
This is How We Dew (Mountain Dew)	2012
Win from Within (Gatorade)	2012
Polar Bowl	2012
Make Interesting Happen (Sierra Mist)	2014
Out of the Blue	2015
Pepsi Generations	2018
That’s What I Like	2020
Greatest of All Time (GOAT) Camp	2020
<i>Branded Juice Campaigns</i> (national) (n = 9)	

Memories (Welch's)	1994
Bite into It (Minute Maid orange juice, Coca-Cola)	1997
100% Juice (Northland cranberry juice)	1997
We Only Pick the Best Fruit (Ocean Spray)	1998
Squeeze the Day (Minute Maid orange juice, Coca-Cola)	1999
Introducing Simply Orange...100% Unfooled Around With (Minute Maid orange juice, Coca-Cola)	2001
Squeeze, It's a Natural (Tropicana, PepsiCo)	2009
Wake Up Your MMOJO (Minute Maid orange juice, Coca-Cola)	2011
Tap into Nature (Tropicana, PepsiCo)	2012
Branded Coffee Campaigns (national) (<i>n</i> = 2)	
Sophisticated Taste (Taster's Choice instant coffee, Nescafe, Nestle)	1990
The Coffee for Intense Taste (Nescafe coffee, Nestle)	1997
Branded Water Campaigns (national) (<i>n</i> = 5)	
It's a Brett Favre Thing (Real Pure water & sports drinks)	2000
L'Original (Evian)	2000
We Promise Nothing (Aquafina, PepsiCo)	2002
Evian: Your Natural Source of Youth	2004
I Wanna Hashtag #Liveyoung	2018
Branded Non-Dairy, Plant-Based Milk Campaigns (national) (<i>n</i> = 3)	
Get Your Soy with Silk	2000
Silk: Milk of the Land (Danone North America, almond milk)	2021
Wow No Cow (Oatly, oat milk)	2021
2. CSR, public relations and cause marketing campaigns (<i>n</i> = 16)	
<i>The American Beverage Association</i> national) (<i>n</i> = 1)	
The Mixify Campaign / The Balance Calorie Initiative (Los Angeles, CA; Little Rock, AR; Mississippi Delta; Montgomery, AL; and NYC, NY)	2014
<i>The Coca-Cola Company</i> national) (<i>n</i> = 5)	

Live Positively (CSR campaign)	2010
Coca-Cola Every Bottle has a Story (sustainability campaign)	2011
The Great Meal/Together Tastes Better	2020
Together We Must	2020
Refreshing the World and Making a Difference	2021
<i>PepsiCo, Inc.</i> national) (<i>n</i> = 7)	
Helping Children Get Clean Water (Ethos water, Starbucks/PepsiCo)	2007
Pepsi Refresh Project (CSR)	2010
Pepsi We Inspire	2010
Black Lives Matter	2017
Black Art Rising (LIFEWTR)	2020
Food for Good	2020
Life Unseen	2021
<i>Danone North America</i> national) (<i>n</i> = 1)	
Drink 1, Give 10 / 1L=10L for Africa (Volvic water, Danone)	2008
<i>Nestlé North America</i> national) (<i>n</i> = 2)	
Nestlé Waters Challenge	2019
Nestlé Pure Life	2019
3. Social marketing campaigns (national) (<i>n</i> = 20)	
<i>Fluid Cow's Milk Campaigns</i> (<i>n</i> = 11)	
Every Body Needs Milk (California Milk Producers Advisory Board)	1970s
Milk. It Does a Body Good (America's Dairy Farmers & National Dairy Board)	Late 1980s
Lowfat Milk Campaign (New York City, NY)	1990
1% or Less (West Virginia, California, Hawaii and Oklahoma)	1995
Got Milk? / Toma Leche? (Milk Processor Education Program, nationwide)	1995
Milk Mustache (Milk Processor Education Program, nationwide)	1995
Milk Made Better (Suiza Foods – dairy processor & distributor)	2000
White Gold (California Milk Processor Board)	2008
Milk Life (Milk Processor Education Program, National)	2014

Source: Kraak, V.I.; Consavage Stanley K.; Harrigan, P.B.; Zhou, M. How have media campaigns been used to promote and discourage healthy and unhealthy beverages in the United States? A systematic scoping review to inform future research to reduce sugary beverage health risks to Americans. *Obes. Rev.* **2022**, *23*, e13425. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13425>.

Choose 1% Milk (Oklahoma)	2014
You're Gonna Need Milk with That. Got Milk? (Milk Processor Education Program, Re-launched)	2020
<i>Water and Juice Promotion Campaigns (national) (n = 9)</i>	
Drink Up! (Partnership for Healthier America)	2013-2016
Live Sugarfreed (rural KY, TN, VA)	2015
One Less Challenge (Delaware)	2015
Kim and Pura (New York City, NY)	2016
NJ Live Sugarfreed	2017
Sip Smarter – Every Day Begins with a Sip (Juice Products Association, national)	2018
Choose Water Not Sugary Drinks! (Healthy Berkeley Partnership, CA)	2020
Skip the Sugar, Choose Water (Albany, CA)	2020
Be Ready. Be Hydrated. Drink Water (Seattle, WA)	2020
4. Public information, awareness, education or health promotion campaigns (n = 27)	
Get Coke Out of Seattle Schools (Seattle, WA)	1996
Rethink Your Drink (San Francisco, CA)	2008
Are You Pouring on the Pounds? (New York City, NY)	2009
Drinks Destroy Teeth (Indiana Dental Association, statewide)	2010
Rethink Your Drink (Cook County, IL)	2010

Are You Pouring on the Pounds (San Francisco, CA)	2010
FatSmack (Boston, MA)	2011
Life's Sweeter with Fewer Sugary Drinks (Boston, MA; Los Angeles, CA; Philadelphia, PA; San Antonio, TX and Seattle, WA)	2011
Sugar Pack (Los Angeles County, CA)	2011
Sugar Bites (Contra Costa County, CA)	2011
It Starts Here (Portland & Multnomah County, OR)	2011
Get Healthy Philly (Philadelphia, PA)	2011
Howard County Unsweetened (Howard County, MD)	2012
Rev Your Bev (Virginia statewide)	2013
Sugar Smarts / Azucar Sabia (Boston, MA)	2013
Drink Yourself Sick / Your Kids Could Be Drinking Themselves Sick (New York City, NY)	2013
Rethink your Drink (San Diego, CA)	2012
Sounds Healthy (New York City, NY)	2013
Cavities Get Around (Delta Dental of Colorado Foundation, CO)	2014
Rethink Your Drink (CDC, in cities nationwide)	2015
Choose Water (Los Angeles, CA)	2015
Drink NYC Tap Water (New York City, NY)	2016
Sour Side of Sweet (New York City, NY)	2017
Hidden Sugar (Denver, CO)	2017
Rethink Your Drink (Arkansas statewide)	2017
Healthy for Good Sip Smarter (American Heart Association)	2018

Healthy Drinks Healthy Kids (RWJF Healthy Eating Research, national)	2020
5. Media advocacy or countermarketing campaigns (n = 10)	
Global Dump Soft Drinks (national and international)	2007
Dunk the Junk (San Francisco, CA)	2011
The Real Bears (CSPI, national)	2012
Soda Sucks (California)	2012
Kick the Can (California and national)	2012
Coming Together: Translated (CSPI)	2013
The Bigger Picture (San Francisco, CA)	2013
'Share a Coke' With Obesity (Center for Science in the Public Interest)	2015
Change the Tune (CSPI)	2015
Open Truth Now (San Francisco, CA)	2015
6. Political or public policy campaigns (n = 23)	
Richmond Fit for Life (Richmond, CA)	2012
No on N (Richmond, CA)	2012
Healthy Diné Nation Act (Navajo Nation)	2014
Choose Health SF (San Francisco, CA)	2014
No SF Beverage Tax / No on E (San Francisco, CA)	2014
No Berkeley Beverage Tax (ABA anti-tax, Berkeley, CA)	2014
Vote Yes on Measure D / Berkeley vs. Big Soda (pro-tax, Berkeley, CA)	2014
Vote Yes on Measure HH to Protect Our Children's Health / Oakland vs. Big Soda (pro-tax, Oakland, CA)	2016
No Oakland Grocery Tax and No on HH (Oakland, CA, ABA-supported, anti-tax)	2016
Vote Yes on Proposition V (pro-tax, San Francisco, CA)	2016
No on V / Enough is Enough: Keep Our Groceries Tax Free (anti-tax, San Francisco, CA)	2016
Yes on O1 (Albany, CA)	2016
No on O1 (Albany, CA)	2016

Source: Kraak, V.I.; Consavage Stanley K.; Harrigan, P.B.; Zhou, M. How have media campaigns been used to promote and discourage healthy and unhealthy beverages in the United States? A systematic scoping review to inform future research to reduce sugary beverage health risks to Americans. *Obes. Rev.* **2022**, *23*, e13425. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obr.13425>.

Vote Yes on Soda Because Our Kids are Worth It! (Philadelphia, PA)	2016
No Philly Grocery Tax	2016
Healthy Boulder Kids Campaign (Boulder, CO)	2016
Pre-K for Santa Fe (pro-tax, Santa Fe, NM)	2017
Better Way for Santa Fe & Pre-K (anti-tax, Santa Fe, NM)	2017
Seattle Healthy Kids Coalition (Seattle, WA)	2018
Keep Seattle Liveable for All (Seattle, WA)	2017
Yes! to Affordable Groceries (anti-tax, Washington, WA)	2017
Vote Yes on Measure 103 to Keep Our Groceries Tax Free (anti-tax, Oregon)	2017
Keep Groceries Affordable Act of 2018	2018

Fair Use Evaluation Documentation

Compiled using the **Fair Use Evaluator** [cc] 2008 Michael Brewer & the Office for Information Technology Policy, <http://librarycopyright.net/fairuse/>

Name:	Nicole Leary, MS
Job Title:	PhD Student and Graduate Teaching Assistant
Institution:	Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Title of Work Used:	Trademark or copyright images from U.S. beverage campaigns
Copyright Holder:	Global, national, regional and local companies and organizations, including multinational beverage companies, U.S. based nonprofits, advocacy groups, and state and local governments
Publication Status:	Published
Publisher:	Organizations who have funded or helped implement U.S. beverage campaigns
Place of Publication:	Internet, organization websites, print media
Publication Year:	Varies based on campaign date
Description of Work:	These images will be included in one figure in a manuscript titled "How Have Media Campaigns Promoted Beverages in the United States? A Qualitative Content Analysis of Campaign Taglines, Slogans and Images to Promote Healthy Hydration and Reduce Sugary Beverage Health Risks"
Date of Evaluation:	February 7, 2023
Date of Intended Use:	February 7, 2023

Describe the **Purpose** and Character of Your Intended Use:

[+] Use is for "criticism, comment, news reporting, teaching, (including multiple print copies for classroom use), scholarship or research." The images used are a portion of a qualitative content analysis of U.S. beverage media campaigns used as part of a research study. The use of these images is for research purposes only and the authors will not receive any monetary contribution for the use of these images.

[+] Use is transformative, i.e. it uses the existing work in a new way (creates an index to the work) or for a new purpose (parody, pastiche, instructional materials, etc.) Transformative works are favored because the purpose of U.S. Copyright Law is to encourage the development and dissemination of new knowledge to benefit the public and thereby advance learning.

[+] Use is socially beneficial (promotes the creation of new knowledge, learning, etc.) The study is beneficial because it promotes the creation of new knowledge and learning through its analysis of the nature and content of persuasive appeals and graphic images used to promote healthy hydration or discourage sugary beverages. The results of this study will suggest future research and inform communication to encourage healthy beverages and hydration to reduce sugary beverage risk factors among U.S. Americans.

[+] Use is clearly defined and is restricted in scope (limited duration, not iterative, restricted access, etc.). The images

will only be used for research and educational purposes.
[+] Use is one-time, or is only occasional or spontaneous.

Describe the **Nature** of Your Intended Use of the Copyrighted Work:

[+] Work to be used has been previously PUBLISHED. The images being used in the research study have been previously published on the internet, organizational websites or in print media. The images will be used during content analysis. The images be will submitted in the in a peer-reviewed journal as a visual representation of a media campaign typology including examples of taglines, slogans, and images to promote or discourage sugary beverages and encourage healthy hydration.

Describe the **Amount** of Your Intended Use in Relation to the Copyrighted Work as a Whole:

[+] The portion used is not the "heart" of the work (the portion considered most central to the work as a whole). The qualitative content analysis of campaigns identified during a previous study represents the main portion considered most central to this work. The images will be provided as a visual representation for the campaigns and typology described throughout the published research.
[+] Only the amount required to achieve the stated, socially-beneficial purpose or objective will be used (be that educational, artistic, scholarly, journalistic, etc.) Images will only be used for research or educational purposes to demonstrate a portion of the U.S. beverage media campaigns and their campaign typologies developed in a previous study and used throughout this qualitative analysis.

Describe the **Effect** of Your Intended Use on the Potential Market or Value of the Copyrighted Work:

[+] Use of the work minimizes the potential for unauthorized use that could impact its value (i.e. steps are taken to ensure the content is not used outside of the stated purpose or audience). The images will only be used for the purposes included in this fair use evaluation document. The images will be used within a figure to be published in a peer-review journal. The audience of the peer-reviewed journal is academics and health professionals.
[+] Proper attribution will be given with the intended use.

The Average **"Fairness Level,"** Based on Your Rating of Each of the 4

Factors, Is:

[see tool disclaimer for important clarifying information]:

Based on the information and justification I have provided above, I, Nicole Leary, MS, am asserting this use is **FAIR** under Section 107 of the U.S. Copyright Code.

Signature: Nicole Leary

Date of Signature: 02/07/2023

***Disclaimer:** This document is intended to help you collect, organize & archive the information you might need to support your fair use evaluation. It is not a source of legal advice or assistance. The results are only as good as the input you have provided by are intended to suggest next steps, and not to provide a final judgment. It is recommended that you share this evaluation with a copyright specialist before proceeding with your intended use.